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D6.2 Pilot Sites Preparation V2

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4PublicPolicy	Artificial Intelligence for Public Policy
API	Application Programming Interface
CDG	Comune di Genova
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DAEM	Dimos Athinaion Epicheirisi Michanografisis
DL	Deep Learning
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HPC	High Performance Computing
HW	Hardware
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
ML	Machine Learning
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organistaions
NLP	Natural Language Processing
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SW	Software
SYDIPA	Municipal Police Infringement Management System
UI	User Interface
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable's first iteration (D6.1 Pilots Sites Preparation V1) included a report on the preliminary preparations that must be made at each of the five (5) pilot sites to guarantee that they are ready for pilot operations. More precisely, analysis was done on the deployment and validation of the hardware and middleware infrastructure required for the installation and operation of the project's pilot systems at the 5 pilot sites.

Additionally, the pilots' early plans for including and mobilising local stakeholders (such as decision-makers, people, businesses, researchers, and academics, etc.) as well as the strategy for training stakeholders to assist them in interacting with the pilot systems and the VPME were provided.

Last but not least, the tasks in WP9's ethical management work package were used to highlight the ethical management activities (such as informed consent) that must be successfully performed before the project's pilot systems can be deployed and used at its five pilot sites.

Similar to the first version, the second version of the deliverable (D6.2 Pilots Site Preparation V2) will provide a comprehensive report of the ongoing preparation operations being carried out at the 5 pilot sites to get them ready for pilot operation.

The deployment of the hardware and software infrastructure required for the operation of the pilots' systems, as was the case in the first version of this deliverable, will be included in the preparation activities necessary for the implementation process. In addition to the infrastructure needed for pilots, data availability and local systems suitability for operations and implementation activities will also be reported.

Additionally, the pilots' involvement plan for mobilising and involving stakeholders in the development, validation, and evaluation of the VPME solutions, the creation, development, validation, and evaluation of the policies, the validation of the pilots' business models, and the further investigation of business and market opportunities is described. Also, the training plan created with the intention of actively including relevant beneficiaries in the use of the pilot systems and the VPME will be reported along with the pilots' engagement strategies.

Finally, a status update of the ethical management provisions, as specified in the deliverables WP9, that are part of the pilot preparation phase will be given.

This report's main objective is to verify that the pilots have installed the infrastructure and equipment necessary for them to operate the pilot systems. In order to involve the local ecosystems, it is also imperative that the pilots take the required steps. Not to mention, another goal of this report is to help pilots uphold their ethical and legal commitments.

In a nutshell, the current document contains all the required information on the preparation steps that must be followed by the pilots over the course of this project to ensure the effective pilots' operation.

In order to obtain all of this pertinent data, a continuous partnership with the pilots was established and upheld in order to monitor the development of the preparation activities detailed in this report.

Additionally, in order to ensure that the pilots are described in a consistent manner and to make it easier to compare and evaluate the progress and performance of the pilots, a common template was also utilised for all the pilots involved in order to give an overview of the progress of the pilots' preparation activities.

Overall, it can be shown from examining the pilots' preparation activities that there are different technical needs for each pilot case when it comes to deploying and running the project's pilot systems. For instance, pilots will follow several procedures with regard to the deployment of the required tools and infrastructure, the accessibility of data, and the setup of local systems that are already in place. However, a common strategy was developed and suggested for adoption by all pilots as far as bringing together local stakeholders. The same holds true for carrying out the necessary ethical activities.

It is critical to emphasise how important the aforementioned planning was for the implementation of the early findings reported in the first round of the pilots' implementation deliverables (D6.3, D6.5, D6.7, D6.9, D6.11). As the project progresses, more implementation and integration results will be generated, and they will be further elaborated in the second version of the implementation deliverables due in M33 (see D6.4, D6.6, D6.8, D6.10, D6.12).

All things considered, the WP6 will continue to work closely with all the pilots as the project moves forward in order to address any risks or concerns that may develop and to make sure that all the preparation activities necessary for the final operation of the pilots' systems are on track.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP6

The WP6 is the pilot's work-package that is devoted to deploying, operating, validating and evaluating the pilot systems with the active engagement of the public authorities of the consortium.

The main objectives are as follow:

- Undertake preparatory activities at the five (5) pilot sites towards their readiness for the pilot operations.
- Customise and deploy the AI4PublicPolicy outcomes in-line with the requirements and needs of the 5 pilot sites.
- Operate and validate the AI4PublicPolicy platform in different use cases and contexts in the 5 pilot sites.
- Evaluate the pilot systems from a technical and a business perspective.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable (D6.2 Pilot Sites Preparation), the second in a series of two, is to provide a report on the phases completed by the pilots in order to be ready for the pilots' system implementation and operation. The following are some of the preparation's phases:

- Deployment and validation of the required hardware and software infrastructure that will support the pilots.
- Mobilisation and engagement of local stakeholders (e.g., policy makers, citizens, businesses, etc.), as well as their proper training to engage with the pilot systems and the VPME.
- Completion of ethical management activities (e.g., informed consent) based on the methodology provided by the ethical management task in WP9.

The first implementation results are presented in the first version of the pilots' implementation deliverables (see D6.3, D6.5, D6.7, D6.9, D6.11,) as a result of these preparation activities, while more thorough implementation results will be reported in the second version of the pilots' implementation deliverables that will be submitted in M33 (D6.4, D6.6, D6.8, D6.10, D6.12).

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

This document is divided into the following chapters:

- **Section 1** provides an overview of the AI4PublicPolicy project while the scope of the WP6 and the current report along with its structure are presented. Furthermore, a roadmap for the methodology and preparation activities is provided.
- **Sections 2,3,4,5, and 6** present a report of the preparation activities that the DAEM, CDG, NIC, LIS and BURGAS pilots completed in order to be ready for the pilot operations and implementation. More specifically, the pilots will provide us with additional information on the hardware (HW) and software (SW) required for collecting raw data, making real-time datasets available to implementation teams and for ensuring access to the VPME. Additionally, the process for making historical datasets available to implementation teams are presented, as are legacy systems that may need to be integrated with AI4PublicPolicy pilot implementations. In addition to the necessary infrastructure and the available data, the pilots' stakeholders' involvement and training plan are provided. Finally, a status report of the completion of the ethical management activities will also be given.
- **Section 7** summarises the main conclusion points and key findings of the preparation activities and indicates future directions for pilots' future preparatory activities.

1.5 Methodology

The approach, procedures, and logic used to create this report will be briefly described in this part. The same methodology used to generate the first version of this report (see D6.1) was applied to gather the information on the pilots' preparations needed to guarantee that they were prepared for the implementation phases.

The work that needed to be done was first divided into seven components, each of which had been individually discussed with the pilots in order to gather the necessary information. More specifically, pilots were asked to provide details on HW/SW required for gathering raw data, for providing the implementation teams with access to the real-time and historical pilot datasets, for using the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources, and for any legacy systems that may need to be integrated with AI4PublicPolicy implementations.

Additionally, pilots were asked to provide information on the engagement plan of the relevant beneficiaries involved at the different stages of the project in order to elaborate further on the stakeholders' involvement plan already supplied in the first version of this report (see D6.1).

As for the training plan, pilots are working on it and it is still a work in progress which depends to a great extent on the development of the technical components and their availability.

The final action assigned to pilots was pertinent to the project's requirement for reporting on ethical management activities. However, it is important to mention that this is an ongoing process and that there is a continuous collaboration between the legal partners and the pilots where needed.

We scheduled biweekly WP6 pilot sessions to cover the pertinent subjects as well as additional open activities linked to the AI4PublicPolicy project in order to gather all the aforementioned information. In addition to the biweekly sessions, we arranged bilateral meetings with pilots when it was judged appropriate to examine each pilot situation specifically.

Overall, the aforementioned method has greatly aided us in systematic discussion with the pilots throughout the preparation of this report and in keeping up with all developments pertaining to the preparation tasks that must be completed at the pilots' locations to ensure their readiness for system operations. In order to describe pilots similarly and make it possible for comparisons and evaluations of the pilots' progress in the future, we also chose to build and use the same template for describing all pilots in a similar way.

1.6 Preparations' Activities Plan

In this section, the structure of the preparation activities plan related to pilots' infrastructure, mobilisation and training of stakeholders as well the completion of ethical activities is provided.

In order to facilitate easier comparison between the pilots, it is intended, as was already noted above, that a uniform set of guidelines is provided.

1.6.1 Pilot infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

This first section is devoted to the preparation activities to deploy the necessary infrastructure, the availability of real-time and historical data and to discuss the local systems that are in place and might need to be integrated with the pilots' implementation systems.

1.6.1.1 HW/SW for raw data collection

The equipment needed for gathering raw data are covered in this section (e.g., sensors etc.). It is essential to go into detail about the infrastructure needed by the pilots to complete this procedure because this is where all data analysis starts. Pilots will provide updates on any additional HW/SW that may have been deployed since the first version of this deliverable was submitted or that may need to be deployed as the project moves forward in this second version.

1.6.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

Pilots will refer to the historical data for each of the datasets listed in the D2.3 in this section, where applicable.

1.6.1.3 HW/SW to make real-time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

In this section, the pilots will describe the HW/SW (e.g., local servers, APIs etc.) required to provide the implementation teams with real-time datasets.

1.6.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources

The equipment and setup needed to access the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources will be covered in this section. Pilots are specifically required to provide information on the HW/SW (including personal laptops, dedicated workstations, operational rooms, etc.) they intend to use to ensure their access.

1.6.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to be integrated with AI4PP pilot implementations

This section is devoted to the pilots' legacy systems that are currently in use and may need to be merged with the AI4PublicPolicy pilot implementations during the course of this project.

1.6.2 Stakeholders' involvement and training plan

This section is also devoted to providing the pilots' activities plan in order to mobilise and engage local stakeholders (such as citizens, policy makers, businesses, etc.) in the creation, development, refinement, and evaluation of policies, the development, validation and evaluation of the VPME solutions as well as the validation of the pilots' business models along with the further exploration of business and market opportunities.

There has been a significant effort on the part of the pilots to increase the active participation and encourage the strong involvement of citizens and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in the creation, development, validation, and evaluation of policies, as well as of the technical solutions. In a similar vein, pilots have made an effort to track down and seek collaboration with relevant stakeholders who can significantly contribute to the validation and evaluation of the project's technical components by offering us feedback that can be helpful for the development of the tools in the future. In order to help us even further explore business and market opportunities, key business and market specialists will also be involved.

A common co-creation plan for the pilots has been created and will be used throughout the project to accomplish the engagement of stakeholders from their local ecosystems (see 5.1 in D6.3, D6.5, D6.7, D6.9, D6.11). In addition to co-creation activities, pilots have developed strategies to actively involve stakeholders in the assessment of policies by taking into account their insightful input (see section 4 in D6.3, D6.5, D6.7, D6.9, D6.11).

In addition, this section will also outline the pilots' plan in order to provide with the proper training the relevant stakeholders with the goal of involving them with the pilots' system and the usage of the VPME (see also sections 5.2 in D6.3, D6.5, D6.7, D6.9, D6.11). Even though the pilots have already developed their initial training plan, this is a work in progress as it much depends on the development of the VPME solutions and their availability.

Taking everything into consideration, all the above preparation activities are of utmost importance and go in line with the overall project's objective to follow a co-creation approach in the creation,

development, validation and evaluation of the policies and of the technical solutions, improve civic involvement, boost transparency and trust in the policy-making processes.

In the next sections, the preparation activities undertaken by each of the pilots will be described in more detail.

1.6.3 Pilots' ethical management activities' completion

As part of the pilot preparation phase, all pilots are required to fulfil the ethical management tasks listed in the table below and described in more detail in the deliverables of WP9. As part of this deliverable, each pilot must produce a status report on the accomplishment of the tasks mentioned in the table below.

It is crucial to remember that in addition to carrying out the required ethical activities listed in the table below, continuing actions are also ongoing to ensure legal and ethical compliance and that the project conforms with applicable laws and regulations. In this direction, pilots work closely with the appropriate legal partners as needed to ensure they adhere to ethical principles.

Table 1. Ethical management activities completion

Activity	Deliverable of Reference
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research	D9.1
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place	D9.2
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable	D9.3
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the pilot technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted	D9.4
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques	D9.5
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file	D9.6
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements	D9.7
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted	D9.8
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This also includes an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 GDPR 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted	D9.9
In D9.10, five issues have been discussed regarding the technology developed in the project: biases, accountability, literacy, quality of the data	D9.10

and policy validation. These issues have been discussed in the form of a questionnaire (see appendix III in D9.3)	
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2 DAEM Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

2.1 Pilot Infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

2.1.1 HW/SW for raw data collection

As stated in the earlier draft of this deliverable, no additional HW/SW will need to be deployed for the DAEM pilot in order to gather raw data. Using the mobile apps from DAEM and Novoville, all datasets that will be accessible for this pilot (as specified in deliverable D2.3) will be gathered. If new datasets are needed in the project's later phases, the focus will be on identifying established data providers and/or open-source data pools to collect them from.

2.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

No further historical data was provided by the DAEM pilot beyond what was already disclosed in the initial draft of the deliverable. The whole quantity of historical data, which covered a 12-month period, was delivered to the implementation teams in CSV format, fully anonymized and confidential, and in accordance with the dataset requirements of the D2.3 deliverable.

Historical datasets for the following datasets were provided:

- Incident reports
- Wallet transactions
- Parking transactions

2.1.3 HW/SW to make real-time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

Before the real-time data are made available to the implementation teams, are stored locally on servers and are only accessible to authorised individuals. In this manner, the data is kept in a central location and is accessible across a shared network.

Datasets in both stored and in-motion forms can be provided to the implementation teams (as streams of data).

Data will be accessible for all datasets via CSV outputs from the Novoville app databases. In order for the implementation teams to have access to these CSV exports, they can be uploaded via the VPME dataset management component. Alternatively, the publicly accessible datasets could also be added to the Policy and Dataset Catalogue.

In terms of the data streams, Novoville and DAEM may need to create REST APIs as the project progresses for all requested datasets. To give the implementation team access to real-time data, these REST APIs (endpoints) can also be added to the relevant VPME dataset management component. The section Dataset Collection and Management in the D2.6 & D2.7 has more details about the collection of real-time data.

The Policy and Dataset Catalogue may also provide access to the implementation teams to the real-time datasets that are made publicly available.

2.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOOSC/EGI resources

Throughout the course of this project, personal computers and dedicated workstations that will be located at DAEM facilities will be used to ensure access to the pilot VPME UI and EOOSC/EGI services.

As the project moves forward, the pilots already have some preliminary plans for the workstation setup and the operations rooms that will be set up temporarily or permanently to access the VPME and EOOSC/EGI resources and to subsequently give the necessary training in the use of the VPME to pertinent beneficiaries and stakeholders.

To access the VPME and EOOSC/EGI resources, however, more specifications and a more detailed plan of the HW/SW will be defined later as the project moves forward and provided in greater depth in the second version of the pilots' implementation deliverables (D6.4).

2.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to be integrated with AI4PP pilot implementations

The Municipal Police Infringement Management System ([SYDIPA](#)), which DAEM built and is already in use for handling the penalties imposed, is one of the legacy systems at the DAEM pilot. There are currently no use cases or user stories that have an impact on this legacy system in its current state.

At the second round of co-creation workshops with the Athens Municipal Police, ideas on utilising legacy data from SYDIPA emerged and are currently under discussion with the Athens Municipal Police. Any new use cases and/or policies using these data will be uploaded to the VPME and will be further discussed in the second version of the pilot implementation deliverable (D6.4).

2.2 Stakeholders’ involvement and training plan

This section is devoted to the preparation activities taken by the DAEM pilot in order to achieve the stakeholders’ involvement as well as their proper training to engage with the pilot systems and the VPME technical solutions.

The DAEM pilot moved forward with the process of **identifying pertinent stakeholders** as a first step in this approach. An initial list of stakeholders, including department heads, city employees, city workers, and citizens, was provided in the first draft of this deliverable (see section 2.2 in D6.1). The DAEM pilot has increased this list as the project develops by identifying additional beneficiaries. In addition to the stakeholders listed above, additional stakeholder groups (such as associations, researchers and academic, business and market specialists) have been taken into consideration, as shown in table 2, to be more thoroughly involved at the various stages of the project.

The DAEM pilot went on to **identify the involvement plan** for each group of stakeholders as the following stage after identifying the stakeholders. As can be seen from the table below, various stakeholders will be involved at different stages of the project and will significantly contribute to the creation, development, improvement and evaluation of the policies, the validation and evaluation of the VPME technical solutions, and the further exploration of business and market opportunities.

The DAEM pilot will follow the co-creation plan created for all pilots in order to achieve the involvement of the stakeholders (see 5.1 in D6.3). The first round of co-creation activities concentrated on integrating the use cases and user stories; however, the second round will involve citizens and NGOs to discuss the policies, and their initial outcomes will be presented to receive input (see section 4 in D6.3). Additionally, the DAEM pilot intends to actively involve stakeholders, such as the Athens Municipal Police, in the assessment of policies by providing them with the chance to offer their views and provide valuable insights.

In addition to participating in the policy-making process, stakeholders will have the ability to examine and test the VPME technical solutions. In the second round of co-creation workshops, they will initially be given a demonstration of the VPME. Later on, in the project (in the third co-creation phase), they will have the opportunity to assess the integrated solutions and express their ideas by answering specially crafted questionnaires.

The DAEM pilot outlined the appropriate **training plan** based on the needs of each stakeholder after identifying the relevant stakeholders and their involvement strategy (see 5.2 in D6.3). It is crucial to note that this is a work-in-progress that is dependent on the creation and availability of the necessary tools.

The categories of stakeholders and the involvement and training strategy are described for the DAEM pilot in the table below.

Table 2. Stakeholders’ involvement and training plan of DAEM Pilot

Type of Stakeholder	Involvement Plan	Training Plan
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<p>Citizens groups and associations (e.g., NGOs)</p>	<p>Involvement in the discussions on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of policies by participating in surveys and providing their feedback</p> <p>Participation in the development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable insights</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the VPME solutions by providing feedback on to what extent the tools meet their needs</p>	<p>They do not require training on the VPME.</p> <p>However, in order for the VPME tools to more accurately reflect and better accommodate the policy development cycle taking into account citizens' feedback, their opinions on the use cases and user stories will be taken into consideration.</p>
<p>Public and local authorities (e.g., policy makers, head of departments, City's employees etc.)</p>	<p>Involvement in the discussions on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Provide valuable feedback on the current processes and resources of the Municipality</p> <p>Contribution to the efficient development of the tools by proving constructive input and requirements on the tools</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the prototype demonstrators and the VPME integrated solutions by testing the solutions and providing feedback</p> <p>Act as end-users that will use the VPME solutions to manage policy development and optimisation process based on AI technologies</p>	<p>Training is required as they will be also end-users of the VPME solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at the DAEM premises</p> <p>The training will be given by DAEM and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>

	<p>Assisting with the business models creation and validation</p>	
<p>Research and academia experts (e.g., AI experts etc.)</p>	<p>Contribution to the efficient development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable feedback</p> <p>Offer opportunities for collaboration with other projects</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potential end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at the DAEM premises</p> <p>The training will be given by DAEM and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>
<p>Companies, business and market experts</p>	<p>Assisting with the business model creation process</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the business models at a later stage of the project</p> <p>Assisting with the AI4PublicPolicy solutions to market by incorporating them into their products and providing feedback on its performance in a real-world setting</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potential end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at the DAEM premises</p> <p>The training will be given by DAEM and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>

2.3 Ethical management activities completion

As part of the pilot preparation phase, all pilots are required to fulfil the ethical management tasks listed in the table below and described in more detail in the deliverables of WP9. As part of this deliverable, the DAEM pilot provides a status report on the accomplishment of the tasks mentioned in the table below.

It is crucial to remember that in addition to carrying out the required ethical activities listed in the table below, continuing actions are also ongoing to ensure legal and ethical compliance and that the project conforms with applicable laws and regulations. In this direction, pilots work closely with the appropriate legal partners as needed to ensure they adhere to ethical principles.

Table 3. Ethical management activities completion of DAEM Pilot

Activity	Deliverable of Reference	Status (Done/Pending)
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place	D9.2	Done
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable	D9.3	Done
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted	D9.4	Pending (deliverable due M36)
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements	D9.7	Done
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 GDPR 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted	D9.9	Done

<p>In D9.10, five issues have been discussed regarding the technology developed in the project: biases, accountability, literacy, quality of the data and policy validation. These issues have been discussed in the form of a questionnaire (see appendix III in D9.3)</p>	<p>D9.10</p>	<p>Done</p>
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3 CDG Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

3.1 Pilot Infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

3.1.1 HW/SW for raw data collection

The CDG pilot has deployed HW in order to gather raw data. This data collection system consists of on-road laser sensors that count and classify passing vehicles.

Each sensor is capable of monitoring two vehicular lanes and could be equipped with varied applications in order to monitor various vehicle characteristics, road surface and weather conditions.

The reliability of the sensors is about 98 percent. In some cases, the combination of monitoring cameras and licence plate reading systems allows complete control of road intersections for mobility purposes.

The data can be extrapolated separately by section and time period thanks to the processing mechanism.

3.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

The historical data can be made available upon request to the City of Genoa, who is the sole owner of this information. The data are displayed within each individual file and are segmented by section and time period. The whole quantity of historical data was delivered to the implementation teams in various formats (e.g. CSV, JSON, excel etc.), fully anonymised and confidential and in accordance with the dataset requirements of the D2.3 deliverable.

So far, the historical data provided by the CDG pilot are listed below:

- Data on accidents collected from Verbatel application
- Meteo data collected by several data logger installed within Genova's Municipality territory
- Public transport data
- Data set on reports/posts submitted by citizens on the "SegnalaCi" application
- Data set on the users submitting the report on the "SegnalaCi" platform
- Data set on Departments or Unit offices in charge of managing reports
- Data set on the type of the post (report, suggestion, claim)
- Data on maintenance interventions achieved from Facility Management Direction of the Municipality of Genoa

3.1.3 HW/SW to make real-time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

The real-time data are stored locally on servers and only authorised people have access to it before they are made available to the implementation teams. In this way the information is accessible through a shared network and kept in a central location.

The implementation teams can receive datasets in both stored and in motion forms (streams of data).

All datasets will have access to stored data via exports (e.g., CSV, JSON etc.). To make these exports accessible to the implementation teams, they can be uploaded using the VPME dataset management component. As an alternative, the publicly accessible datasets could potentially be added to the Policy and Dataset Catalogue.

Without a contract, with the company providing the service, it is not possible to share data in real time with partners. In case this agreement is made, the data streams will be accessible via REST APIs (endpoints) that can be also added to the relevant VPME dataset management component to ensure the implementation team access to the real-time data. For more information related to the collection of real-time data see the section Dataset Collection and Management in the D2.6 & D2.7.

As for the real-time datasets that are publicly available, the implementation teams could also have access via the Policy and Dataset Catalogue.

3.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOOSC/EGI resources

As stated in the first version of the deliverable, personal computers and dedicated workstations that will be located at CDG premises will be used over the course of this project to ensure access to the pilot VPME UI and EOOSC/EGI resources.

As the project progresses, pilots already have some initial plans for the workstation setup and the operation rooms that will be set ad-hoc or permanently for accessing the VPME and EOOSC/EGI resources and to later on to provide the necessary training in the VPME use to relevant beneficiaries and stakeholders.

However, more details and a more concrete plan of the HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOOSC/EGI resources will be defined as the project progresses and provided in more detail in the second version of pilots' implementation deliverables (D6.6).

3.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to be integrated with AI4PP pilot implementations

No legacy systems reported in the CDG pilot that can be considered candidates for possible integration with the AI4PublicPolicy implementations. In case there is a need for such an integration, all the details will be reported in the second version of the pilot implementation deliverable (D6.6).

3.2 Stakeholders' involvement and training plan

This section is devoted to the preparation activities taken by the CDG pilot in order to achieve the stakeholders' involvement as well as their proper training to engage with the pilot systems and the VPME technical solutions.

As a first step in this direction, the CDG pilot proceeded with the **identification of relevant stakeholders**. In the first version of this deliverable, it provided an initial list with stakeholders (see section 3.2 in D6.1). However, since the scope of the pilot has changed the initial stakeholders' list provided is not any more relevant. As a result, the CDG pilot has identified new stakeholders that are pertinent to the current pilot's scope and will be involved at the different phases of the project.

As a next step after the identification of stakeholders, the CDG pilot continued with the **identification of the involvement plan** for each stakeholder category. As it can be seen below, different stakeholders will be involved at different phases of the project and will substantially contribute to the creation, development, refinement and evaluation of the policies as well as the validation and evaluation of the VPME technical solutions. Last but not least, they will also help to further explore the business and market opportunities.

The CDG pilot, in order to achieve the stakeholders' involvement, will follow the co-creation plan that has been developed for all pilots (see 5.1 in D6.5). While in the first round of co-creation activities the focus was on the consolidation of the use cases and user stories, the next round of co-creation activities will involve citizens and possibly NGO's to discuss the policies and their first results will be presented in order to collect feedback. Moreover, the CDG pilot is planning to actively engage stakeholders in the evaluation of policies by giving the opportunity to stakeholders to provide their feedback (see section 4 in D6.5).

Stakeholders will also have the chance to assess and test the VPME technological solutions in addition to their participation in the policy formulation. In the second round of co-creation activities, they will first be given a demonstration of the VPME, and in the third round of co-creation activities, they will have the chance to test the integrated solutions and provide their opinions by answering dedicated questionnaires.

Having identified the relevant stakeholders and their involvement plan, the CDG pilot specified the necessary **training plan** based on the needs of each stakeholder (see section 5.2 in D6.5). However, it is important to mention that this is a process in progress that depends on the development of the required tools and their availability.

In the following table the groups of stakeholders alongside the involvement and training plan is presented for the CDG pilot.

Table 4. Stakeholders' involvement and training plan of CDG Pilot

Type of Stakeholder	Involvement Plan	Training Plan
<p>Citizens groups and associations (e.g., NGOs)</p>	<p>Involvement in the discussions on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of policies by participating in surveys and providing their feedback</p> <p>Participation in the development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable insights</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the VPME solutions by providing feedback on to what extent the tools meet their needs</p> <p>Raise awareness and promote discussions on the topic of road fatalities and serious injuries in the city of Genova</p>	<p>They do not require training on the VPME.</p> <p>However, in order for the VPME tools to more accurately reflect and better accommodate the policy development cycle taking into account citizens' feedback, their opinions on the use cases and user stories will be taken into consideration.</p>
<p>Public and local authorities (e.g., policy makers, head of departments, City's employees etc.)</p>	<p>Involvement in the discussions on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Provide valuable feedback on the current processes and resources of the Municipality</p> <p>Contribution to the efficient development of the tools by proving constructive input and requirements on the tools</p> <p>Evaluation and validation of the prototype demonstrators and the VPME integrated</p>	<p>Training is required as they will be also end-users of the VPME solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at the CDG Municipality premises</p> <p>The training will be given by CDG and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>

	<p>solutions by testing the solutions and providing us with their feedback</p> <p>Act as end-users that will use the VPME solutions to manage policy development and optimisation process based on AI technologies</p> <p>Assisting with the business models creation and validation</p>	
<p>Research and academia experts (e.g., AI experts etc.)</p>	<p>Contribution to the efficient development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable feedback on the solutions</p> <p>Offer opportunities for collaboration with other projects</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potential end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at the CDG Municipality premises</p> <p>The training will be given by CDG and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>
<p>Companies, business and market experts</p>	<p>Assisting with the business model creation process</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the business models at a later stage of the project</p> <p>Assisting with the AI4PublicPolicy solutions to market by incorporating them into their products and providing feedback on its performance in a real-world setting</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potential end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at CDG premises</p> <p>The training will be given by CDG and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>

3.3 Ethical management activities completion

As part of the pilot preparation phase, all pilots are required to fulfil the ethical management tasks listed in the table below and described in more detail in the deliverables of WP9. As part of this deliverable, the CDG pilot provides a status report on the accomplishment of the tasks mentioned in the table below.

It is crucial to remember that in addition to carrying out the required ethical activities listed in the table below, continuing actions are also ongoing to ensure legal and ethical compliance and that the project conforms with applicable laws and regulations. In this direction, pilots work closely with the appropriate legal partners as needed to ensure they adhere to ethical principles.

Table 5. Ethical management activities completion of CDG Pilot

Activity	Deliverable of Reference	Status (Done/Pending)
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place	D9.2	Done
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable	D9.3	Done
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted	D9.4	Pending (deliverable due M36)
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements	D9.7	Done
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 GDPR 2016/679. The risk	D9.9	Done

evaluation and the opinion must be submitted		
<p>In D9.10, five issues have been discussed regarding the technology developed in the project: biases, accountability, literacy, quality of the data and policy validation. These issues have been discussed in the form of a questionnaire (see appendix III in D9.3)</p>	D9.10	Done

4 NIC Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

4.1 Pilot Infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

4.1.1 HW/SW for raw data collection

The NIC pilot will deploy different kinds of HW/SW equipment like sensors and cameras in order to collect raw data. More specifically, six (6) Smart Sense AirQ sensors have been installed. As a result, the NIC pilot is able to track and document various environmental factors such as dust, temperature, air quality, ozone and various pollutants thanks to the presence of multiple environmental sensors. The location of the sensors described above is depicted in the picture below.

As for the noise data is not available as the sensors have not yet been installed but they will be installed in the future.

Figure 2. Installation location of Smart Sense AirQ sensors in NIC pilot

Apart from the sensors installed, the NIC pilot is using CCTV surveillance cameras, which are part of a system with more than 35 cameras installed (see figure 3). More specifically, this system can track down density, vehicle traffic on main roads and identify potential incidents such as traffic violations, abandoned objects, and concentrations of dangerous individuals in real-time (see figure 4). The cameras are integrated with a Smart City Platform, which enables efficient management of the system, and easy communication between the sensors, systems and applications.

In order to collect precise and thorough data, environmental sensors and cameras have been deployed in strategic locations across the city. To keep track of traffic movement and spot potential congestion, cameras are placed at significant crossroads and high-traffic areas. The placement of the cameras has been chosen with care to get the most useful data overall.

Figure 3. Cameras' installation locations in NIC pilot

Figure 4. Traffic statistics for a specific street in NIC pilot

4.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

The NIC pilot provided historical datasets that were sent to the implementation teams in CSV and JSON format fully anonymized and confidential, and in accordance with the dataset specifications of the D2.3 deliverable.

Historical datasets for the following datasets were provided:

- Smart parking management data (covered a 30-days period)
- Monitoring environmental data (covered a 1-year period)

Further historical data such as traffic flow, air quality and weather conditions can be accessed by utilising the Nokia IOC 2.0 API.

4.1.3 HW/SW to make real-time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

Before being made available to the implementation teams, the real-time data are kept locally on servers with access restricted to only authorised users. By doing this, the data is stored in a central location and made available across a shared network.

The implementation teams can receive datasets in both stored and in motion forms (streams of data).

Data that has been stored will be available via file exports (e.g., CSV, JSON etc.). In order for the implementation teams to have access to these outputs, they can be uploaded via the VPME dataset management component. The publicly accessible datasets could also be uploaded to the Policy and Dataset Catalogue.

The real-time data sets of the NIC pilot are made available to the implementation teams through the API for the smart city platform (Nokia IOC 2.0, with a base URL of nokia.smartnicosia.eu/backend/openapi) alongside with the documentation for the Nokia IOC API. By utilising the Nokia IOC 2.0 API, real-time data such as traffic flow, air quality and weather conditions can be accessed. These REST APIs (endpoints) can be also added to the relevant VPME dataset management component to ensure the implementation team access to the real-time data. For more information related to the collection of real-time data see the section Dataset Collection and Management in the D2.6 & D2.7.

As for the real-time datasets that are publicly available, the implementation teams could also have access via the Policy and Dataset Catalogue.

4.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources

Throughout the course of this project, personal computers and dedicated workstations that will be situated at NIC premises will be used to ensure access to the pilot VPME UI and EOSC/EGI services.

As the project moves forward, the pilots already have some preliminary plans for the workstation setup and the operations rooms that will be set up temporarily or permanently for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources and to subsequently give the necessary training in the use of the VPME to pertinent beneficiaries and stakeholders.

To access the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources, however, further details and a more detailed plan of the HW/SW will be established as the project progresses and supplied in greater detail in the second version of the pilots' implementation deliverables (D6.8).

4.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to be integrated with AI4PP pilot implementations

As the NIC pilot moves forward with the AI4PublicPolicy implementations, there may be a need to integrate with the following legacy systems below:

- the back office of the Municipality (YLATIS)
- the Smart City Platform of Nicosia (NOKIA-IOC).

These systems are critical to the operation of the municipality and contain valuable data that could be used to improve the AI4PublicPolicy pilot implementations. By integrating with these legacy systems, the AI4PublicPolicy implementations will be able to be seamlessly integrated into the Municipality's existing infrastructure and processes. The Municipality's back-office would provide access to data related to Municipality operations, while the Nicosia Smart City Platform would provide access to data related to city infrastructure.

The link between the AI4PublicPolicy pilot implementation and the Municipality's YLATIS back office may provide useful information and assistance in certain situations. It is worth noting that the back-office system is out of date and will be replaced by EUAGORAS shortly. As a result, integration with the existing back-office system may not be advantageous at this stage of the project.

Data from multiple city sources are gathered and integrated by the Smart City Nicosia Platform, which may be used to gain insights and guide decisions about the implementations. The capacity to visualise the data gathered by the Smart City Nicosia Platform, which will provide a thorough

perspective of the city's operations and assist stakeholders in making data-driven decisions, is one of the main advantages of this integration. The AI4PublicPolicy teams will be able to identify areas for development and create focused solutions thanks to the data visualisation, which will give an in-depth insight of the city's operations. The implementation teams will also have access to real-time data through this interface, which will be crucial in deciding the suggested project policies. In order to make sure that the pilot implementation is successful, efficient, and in line with the general goals and objectives of the Nicosia Municipality, data will be crucial.

The integration with both systems has the potential to greatly help the Nicosia Municipality achieve its goals of digital transformation and to deliver a range of new digital services that include smart parking, smart waste management, environmental sensors, cameras, video analytics and info points, while it will enhance the pilot implementations.

4.2 Stakeholders' involvement and training plan

This section is devoted to the efforts the NIC pilot undertook to get stakeholders involved and properly trained to interact with the pilot systems and the technical solutions provided by VPME.

The NIC pilot proceeded over to identify the **relevant stakeholders** as a first step in this direction. An initial list of stakeholders was provided in the first iteration of this deliverable (see section 4.2 in D6.1). However, the initial stakeholders list provided is no longer pertinent given that the pilot's scope has been modified. The NIC pilot has therefore discovered new stakeholders who are pertinent to the current pilot's scope and who will be involved during the project's various phases.

The NIC pilot went on to identify the **involvement plan** for each group of stakeholders as the following stage after identifying the stakeholders. As can be seen from the table below, many stakeholders will be involved at various project stages and will significantly help with the creation, improvement and evaluation of the policies as well as the validation and assessment of the VPME technological solutions. Last but not least, they will aid in furthering market and commercial opportunity exploration.

The NIC pilot in order to achieve the stakeholders' involvement will follow the co-creation plan that has been developed for all pilots. Therefore, the NIC pilot will soon organise the first co-creation workshop in order to discuss the scope of the pilot, consolidate the use cases and user stories, and address any stakeholders' needs by taking into consideration their input.

In the next phases of the co-creation workshops, the refinement of the use cases and user stories as well as the pilots' policies will be discussed with the relevant stakeholders, citizens and NGOs. Apart from the civic engagement in the policy development cycle and optimisation process, the NIC pilot is also planning to actively engage stakeholders in the evaluation of policies by giving the opportunity to stakeholders to provide their feedback (see section 4 in D6.7).

Stakeholders will also get the chance to validate and assess the technical solutions of the VPME. In the second round of co-creation workshops, they will first be shown a demonstration of the VPME, then later on in the project (third round of co-creation activities) they will have the chance to evaluate the integrated solutions and share their opinions by answering to dedicated questionnaires.

The NIC pilot outlined the appropriate **training plan** based on the needs of each stakeholder after identifying the key stakeholders and their involvement strategy. It is crucial to note that this is a work-in-progress that depends on the development of the necessary tools.

In the following table the groups of stakeholders alongside the involvement and training plan is presented for the NIC pilot.

Table 6. Stakeholders' involvement and training plan of NIC Pilot

Type of Stakeholder	Involvement Plan	Training Plan
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<p>Citizens groups and associations (e.g., NGOs)</p>	<p>Involvement in the discussions on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of policies by participating in surveys and providing feedback</p> <p>Participation in the development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable insights</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the VPME solutions by providing feedback on to what extent the tools meet their needs</p>	<p>They do not require training on the VPME.</p> <p>However, in order for the VPME tools to more accurately reflect and better accommodate the policy development cycle taking into account citizens' feedback, their opinions on the use cases and user stories will be taken into consideration.</p>
<p>Public and local authorities (e.g., policy makers, head of departments, City's employees etc.)</p>	<p>Involvement in the discussions on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Provide valuable feedback on the current processes and resources of the Municipality</p> <p>Contribution to the efficient development of the tools by proving constructive input and requirements on the tools</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the prototype demonstrators and the VPME integrated solutions by testing the solutions and providing us with their feedback</p> <p>Act as end-users that will use the VPME solutions to manage policy development and optimisation process based on AI technologies</p>	<p>Training is required as they will be also end-users of the VPME solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at the NIC Municipality premises</p> <p>The training will be given by NIC and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>

	<p>Assisting with the business models creation and validation</p>	
<p>Research and academia experts (e.g., AI experts etc.)</p>	<p>Contribution to the efficient development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable feedback on the solutions</p> <p>Offer opportunities for collaboration with other projects</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potential end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at the NIC Municipality premises</p> <p>The training will be given by NIC and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>
<p>Companies, business and market experts</p>	<p>Assisting with the business model creation process</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the business models at a later stage of the project</p> <p>Assisting with the AI4PublicPolicy solutions to market by incorporating them into their products and providing feedback on its performance in a real-world setting</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potent end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at NIC premises</p> <p>The training will be given by NIC and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>

4.3 Ethical management activities completion

As part of the pilot preparation phase, all pilots are required to fulfil the ethical management tasks listed in the table below and described in more detail in the deliverables of WP9. As part of this deliverable, the NIC pilot provides a status report on the accomplishment of the tasks mentioned in the table below.

It is crucial to remember that in addition to carrying out the required ethical activities listed in the table below, continuing actions are also ongoing to ensure legal and ethical compliance and that the project conforms with applicable laws and regulations. In this direction, pilots work closely with the appropriate legal partners as needed to ensure they adhere to ethical principles.

Table 7. Ethical management activities completion of NIC Pilot

Activity Deliverable of Reference Status (Done/Pending)	Deliverable of Reference	Status (Done/Pending)
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place	D9.2	Done
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable	D9.3	Done
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted	D9.4	Pending (deliverable due M36)
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements	D9.7	Done
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an	D9.9	Done

<p>opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 GDPR 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted</p>		
<p>In D9.10, five issues have been discussed regarding the technology developed in the project: biases, accountability, literacy, quality of the data and policy validation. These issues have been discussed in the form of a questionnaire (see appendix III in D9.3)</p>	<p>D9.10</p>	<p>Done</p>

5 LIS Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

5.1 Pilot Infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

5.1.1 HW/SW for raw data collection

Except for the ones that are currently in place for gathering raw data, the LIS pilot will not employ any other sensors or data collection tools. The D2.3 specifies that all datasets necessary for this pilot shall be collected utilising methods already in use.

5.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

The historical data that are available for the following LIS datasets, are listed below:

1. Identification and location of the air quality and meteorology sensors
2. Historical data of the records measured for all parameters
3. Lisbon green structure
4. Lisbon cycling network
5. Lisbon main road network
6. Lisbon secondary road network
7. Data on the number and type of buildings and demographics
8. Electricity consumption by civil parish

The historical data for the above datasets are fetched using the following web services:

1. <https://lisboaaberta.cm-lisboa.pt/index.php/pt>
2. <http://opendata-cml.qart.pt>
3. <https://opendata.arcgis.com/>
4. <http://mapas.ine.pt>
5. <https://api.ipma.pt>
6. <https://e-redes.opendatasoft.com/>

JSON, GeoJSON, and CSV are the formats that are offered for historical data. In D2.3, the particular endpoints for these historical data are described.

Finally, it is crucial to note that the LIS pilot is now looking into other methods for acquiring extra data (images). If any additional information is made available, it will be reported in the LIS pilot's subsequent implementation deliverable (D6.10).

5.1.3 HW/SW to make real-time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

Before the real-time data is made available to the implementation teams, it will first be locally stored on servers with only authorised users having access to it. In this approach, the data is stored centrally and made accessible through a shared network.

Datasets in both stored and in-motion forms are provided to the implementation teams (streams of data).

Ad-hoc CSV exports of the stored data will be available for all datasets. These CSV exports can be uploaded via the VPME dataset management component in order to become available to the implementation teams. Alternatively, the datasets that are publicly available could be also uploaded in the Policy and Dataset Catalogue.

As for the data streams, they will be accessible via APIs and file transfer endpoints using the same links provided in 5.1.2.

To ensure that the implementation team has access to real-time data, the aforementioned endpoints can also be added to the relevant VPME dataset management component, where applicable. The section Dataset Collection and Management in the D2.6 & D2.7 has more details about the selection of real-time data.

The Policy and Dataset Catalogue may also provide access to the implementation teams to the real-time datasets that are made publicly available.

5.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources

Throughout the course of this project, personal computers and dedicated workstations that will be installed at the LIS pilot premises will be used to ensure access to the pilot VPME UI and EOSC/EGI services.

In order to access the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources and later to give the necessary training in the use of the VPME to pertinent beneficiaries and stakeholders, the pilots have already crafted some preliminary plans for the workstation setup and the operation rooms that will be set up temporarily or permanently.

However, in order to access the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources, further specifics and a more thorough plan of the required HW/SW will be provided in the second iteration of the pilots' implementation deliverables (D6.11).

5.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to be integrated with AI4PP pilot implementations

The municipality geographical software system (ArcGIS), which is used to create maps, is viewed by the LIS pilot as a potential system that could be integrated into the AI4PublicPolicy components. However as for now, no additional technical information or integration specifications have been provided for this integration.

Given the capabilities and the flexibility that the AI4PublicPolicy technical components will allow, new use cases that are identified during the implementation phase and call for integration with the ArcGIS platform will have their feasibility and development discussed ad hoc during that phase. The D.10 will incorporate any additional developments on this front.

5.2 Stakeholders' involvement and training plan

This section is devoted to the actions the LIS pilot took to get the stakeholders' support and the appropriate training they need to interact with the pilot systems and the VPME technical solutions.

The LIS pilot moved forward with the process of **identifying relevant stakeholders** as a first step in this approach. This deliverable's initial list of stakeholders included public and local authorities, citizen groups and associations, academic research centres, and businesses and organisations in the energy sector (see section 5.2 in D6.1).

The LIS pilot has improved the involvement plan as the project continues ahead by providing additional information on the various engagement activities assigned to each group of stakeholders who will be more heavily engaged as the project moves forward.

Following the identification of stakeholders, the LIS pilot went on to identify the **involvement plan** for each type of stakeholders. As shown in the table below, various stakeholders will be involved at different stages of the project and will significantly help with the development, improvement, and evaluation of the policies as well as the assessment and validation of the VPME technical solutions. Last but not least, they will aid in furthering market and commercial opportunity exploration.

The LIS pilot in order to achieve the stakeholders' involvement will follow the co-creation plan that has been developed for all pilots (see 5.1 in D6.9). While in the first round of co-creation activities the focus was on the consolidation of the use cases and user stories, the next round of co-creation activities will involve citizens and NGO's to further discuss the policies and their first results will be presented in order to collect feedback. To this end, the LIS pilot will soon hold a co-creation workshop where the civil society will have an active role. In order to maximise participation and attract more

citizens, the event was published in social media well ahead of time. Moreover, the LIS pilot is planning to actively engage stakeholders in the evaluation of policies by giving the opportunity to stakeholders to provide their feedback (see section 4 in D6.9).

In addition, apart from stakeholder’s involvement in the policy development and optimisation process, stakeholders will be given the opportunity to evaluate and validate the VPME technical solutions. In the first place, a demo of the VPME will be presented to them in the second round of co-creation workshops, while in the third co-creation phase they will be given the opportunity to test the integrated solutions and provide their insights by responding to dedicated questionnaires created for this purpose.

Having identified the relevant stakeholders and their involvement plan, the LIS pilot specified the necessary **training plan** based on the needs of each stakeholder (see section 5.2 in D6.9) . More specifically, details on the training location, training materials and the trainers are provided on the table below.

The groups of stakeholders and the involvement and training strategy are described for the LIS pilot in the table below.

Table 8. Stakeholders’ involvement and training plan of LIS Pilot

Type of Stakeholder	Involvement Plan	Training Plan
<p>Citizens groups and associations (e.g., NGOs)</p>	<p>Involvement in the discussions on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of policies by participating in surveys and providing their feedback</p> <p>Participation in the development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable insights</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the VPME solution by providing feedback on to what extent the tools needs their needs</p> <p>Mobilise networks, promote energy literacy and to motivate discussions on the efficiency of the AI-based energy policy-making</p>	<p>They do not require training on the VPME.</p> <p>However, in order for the VPME tools to more accurately reflect and better accommodate the policy development cycle taking into account citizens' feedback, their opinions on the use cases and user stories will be taken into consideration.</p>
	<p>Involvement in the discussions</p>	<p>Training is required as they</p>

<p>Public and local authorities (e.g., policy makers, head of departments, City’s employees etc.)</p>	<p>on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Provide valuable feedback on the current processes and resources of the Municipality</p> <p>Contribution to the efficient development of the tools by proving constructive input and requirements on the tools</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the prototype demonstrators and the VPME integrated solutions by giving them the opportunity to review and test the solutions and provide us with their feedback</p> <p>End-users that will use the VPME solutions to manage policy development and optimisation process based on AI technologies</p> <p>Assisting with the business models creation and validation</p>	<p>will be the end-users of the VPME solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at Lisboa E-nova premises</p> <p>The training will be given by Lisboa E-Nova and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>
<p>Research and academia experts (e.g., AI experts etc.)</p>	<p>Contribution to the efficient development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable feedback on the solutions</p> <p>Offer opportunities for collaboration with other projects</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potential end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at Lisboa E-nova premises</p> <p>The training will be given by Lisboa E-Nova and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>
	<p>Assisting with bringing the AI4PublicPolicy solutions to market by incorporating them into their products and providing feedback on its performance in a real-world</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potent end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at</p>

Companies, business and market experts	setting	Lisboa E-nova premises
	Assisting with the business model creation process	The training will be given by Lisboa E-nova and relevant technical project experts
	Validation and evaluation of the business models at a later stage of the project	The training material is under development

5.3 Ethical management activities completion

As part of the pilot preparation phase, all pilots are required to fulfil the ethical management tasks listed in the table below and described in more detail in the deliverables of WP9. As part of this deliverable, the LIS pilot provides a status report on the accomplishment of the tasks mentioned in the table below.

It is crucial to remember that in addition to carrying out the required ethical activities listed in the table below, continuing actions are also ongoing to ensure legal and ethical compliance and that the project conforms with applicable laws and regulations. In this direction, pilots work closely with the appropriate legal partners as needed to ensure they adhere to ethical principles.

Table 9. Ethical management activities completion of LIS Pilot

Activity Deliverable of Reference Status (Done/Pending)	Deliverable of Reference	Status (Done/Pending)
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place	D9.2	Done
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable	D9.3	Done
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted	D9.4	Pending (deliverable due M36)
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which	D9.7	Done

will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements		
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 GDPR 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted	D9.9	Done
In D9.10, five issues have been discussed regarding the technology developed in the project: biases, accountability, literacy, quality of the data and policy validation. These issues have been discussed in the form of a questionnaire (see appendix III in D9.3)	D9.10	Done

6 BURGAS Pilot Preparation and Transformation Activities Plan

6.1 Pilot Infrastructure, data availability and local systems preparation

6.1.1 HW/SW for raw data collection

The BURGAS pilot will use a system of water pipe sensors that will be put in various locations, as was described in the first draft of this deliverable, to gather raw data. In order to provide more raw data in this direction, the BURGAS pilot has already installed flow metres and vibration sensors in lab settings in partnership with the water utility company (EKSO).

Two experiments were run in a lab setting to gather data that would be utilised to train the AI model. In the first test, only one vibration sensor was utilised (see figure 5), whereas two vibration sensors and a flow metre were employed in the second test (for more information on the results and the technical aspects of these two experiments see section 2.1.2 in D6.11).

Figure 5. First test with a single vibration sensor conducted in BURGAS

The next step is to put sensors on a real-world pipe segment in BURGAS because the two tests mentioned above were completed in a laboratory setting. BURGAS and EKSO will further discuss the installation's technical specifics, which will be presented in the second iteration of the deliverable for the pilot implementation (D6.12).

6.1.2 Process to make historical pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

The BURGAS pilot had already produced historical datasets for a variety of parameters (water flow rate, water pressure, accident frequency, water losses, etc.), as was stated in the first version of this deliverable (see section 6.1.2 in D6.1). The data, however, have not proven useful for teaching the AI because they were not continuously accessible and were not connected to the vibration measurements that the BURGAS pilot is currently working on.

6.1.3 HW/SW to make real-time pilot datasets accessible to implementation teams

Real-time data are stored locally on servers, and only authorised users have access to them before they are made available to the implementation teams, as stated in D6.1 (section 6.1.3). In this manner, the data is kept in a central location and is accessible across a shared network.

Datasets in both stored and in-motion forms are provided to the implementation teams (streams of data).

All datasets' stored data will be available through exports (e.g., CSV, JSON). In order for the implementation teams to have access to these CSV outputs, they can be uploaded via the VPME dataset management component. The publicly accessible datasets could also be added to the Policy and Catalogue.

As for the data streams, all of the stated datasets will be accessed via REST APIs, which may need to be implemented as the project progresses. To give the implementation team access to real-time data, these REST APIs (endpoints) can also be added to the corresponding VPME dataset management component. The section Dataset Collection and Management in the D2.6 & D2.7 has more details about the collection of real-time data.

The Policy and Dataset Catalogue may also provide access to the implementation teams to the real-time datasets that are made publicly available.

6.1.4 HW/SW for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources

Throughout the course of this project, personal computers and dedicated workstations that will be located at BURGAS facilities will be used to ensure access to the pilot VPME UI and EOSC/EGI resources.

As the project moves forward, the pilots already have some preliminary plans for the workstation setup and the operations rooms that will be set up temporarily or permanently for accessing the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources and to subsequently give the necessary training in the use of the VPME to pertinent beneficiaries and stakeholders.

To access the VPME and EOSC/EGI resources, however, more details and a more clear strategy of the HW/SW will be developed and delivered in greater detail in the second version of the pilots implementation deliverable (D6.12).

6.1.5 Legacy systems that may need to be integrated with AI4PP pilot implementations

Candidates for integration with the AI4PP pilot components include a number of legacy systems that are already in use as part of the BURGAS pilot and have been reported in D6.1 (see section 6.1.5). The description of these systems is as follows:

- **Smart city platform:** The Municipality of Burgas runs a smart city platform that functions as the city's digital brain and gathers data from numerous smart technologies and devices that are active in the urban setting.
- **Plasment:** It is a system currently in use to help keep track of water supply and sewerage accidents, the number of water metres, the number of subscribers, and the amounts of collected water.
- **SCADA:** It is a system for control and data acquisition for water quantity, level of the water in water tanks, chlorine, condition of the pumps and their remote control
- **SioPro and Archimed:** Systems used for accounting purposes and record keeping.

However, no additional technical information or integration specifications have been offered in relation to the integration with the aforementioned platforms. The technical viability will be discussed ad hoc during the implementation phase given the capabilities and flexibility that the AI4PublicPolicy technical components will provide, in the event that new use cases are discovered during the implementation phase that demand information exchange between the AI4PublicPolicy components and one or more of the above platforms. Deliverable D6.12 will be updated to reflect any new developments on this front.

6.2 Stakeholders' involvement and training plan

This section is devoted to the preparatory steps that the BURGAS pilot took to ensure that the stakeholders were involved and that they were properly trained to interact with the pilot systems and the VPME technical solutions.

As a first step in this direction, the BURGAS pilot proceeded with the **identification of relevant stakeholders**. In the first version of this deliverable, it provided an initial list with stakeholders including water utility company and municipal administrators, municipal experts, water and IT engineers as well as other third parties (see section 6.2 in D6.1).

As the project moves forward, the BURGAS pilot has expanded this list by identifying more beneficiaries. As depicted in table 10, apart from the stakeholders mentioned above, extra categories of stakeholders have been considered (e.g., citizens group and associations, research and academia, business and market experts, companies of the water sector) to be further involved at the different stages of the project.

As a next step after the identification of stakeholders, the BURGAS pilot continued with the **identification of the involvement plan** for each stakeholder category. As it can be seen below, different stakeholders will be involved at different phases of the project and will substantially contribute to the creation, development, refinement and evaluation of the policies as well as the validation and evaluation of the VPME technical solutions. Last but not least, they will also help to further explore the business and market opportunities.

The BURGAS pilot in order to achieve the stakeholders' involvement will follow the co-creation plan that has been developed for all pilots (see 5.1 in D6.11). In the first round of co-creation activities the focus was on the consolidation of the use cases and user stories. Then, in the next round of co-creation activities will involve stakeholders, citizens and NGOs to discuss the policies and their first results will be presented in order to collect feedback. Moreover, the BURGAS pilot is planning to actively engage stakeholders in the evaluation of policies by giving the opportunity to stakeholders to provide their feedback (see section 4 in D6.11).

In addition, apart from stakeholder's involvement in the policy development and optimisation process, stakeholders will be given the opportunity to evaluate and validate the VPME technical solutions. In the first place, a demo of the VPME will be presented to them in the second phase of co-creation activities, while in the third round of co-creation activities they will be given the opportunity to test the integrated solutions and provide their insights by responding to dedicated questionnaires created for this purpose.

Having identified the relevant stakeholders and their involvement plan, the BURGAS pilot specified the necessary **training plan** based on the needs of each stakeholder (see 5.2 in D6.11). More specifically, details on the training location, training materials and the trainers are provided.

In the following table the groups of stakeholders alongside the involvement and training plan is presented for BURGAS pilot.

Table 10. Stakeholders' involvement and training plan of BIRGAS Pilot

Type of Stakeholder	Involvement Plan	Training Plan
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<p>Citizens groups and associations (e.g., NGOs)</p>	<p>Involvement in the discussions on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of policies by participating in surveys and providing their feedback</p> <p>Participation in the development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable insights</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the VPME solution by providing feedback on to what extent the tools meet their needs</p> <p>Raise awareness and promote discussions on the water losses problems</p>	<p>They do not require training on the VPME.</p> <p>However, in order for the VPME tools to more accurately reflect and better accommodate the policy development cycle taking into account citizens' feedback, their opinions on the use cases and user stories will be taken into consideration</p>
<p>Public and local authorities (e.g., policy makers, head of departments, City's employees etc.)</p>	<p>Involvement in the discussions on the definition, review and update of use cases and user stories</p> <p>Participation in the creation and refinement of policies</p> <p>Provide valuable feedback on the current processes and resources of the Municipality</p> <p>Contribution to the efficient development of the tools by proving constructive input and requirements on the tools</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the prototype demonstrators and the VPME integrated solutions by giving them the opportunity to review and test the solutions and provide us with their feedback</p>	<p>Training is required as they will be the end-users of the VPME solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at the Water Sewerage and Sanitation company facilities</p> <p>The training will be given by BURGAS and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>

	<p>End-users that will use the VPME solutions to manage policy development and optimisation process based on AI technologies</p> <p>Assisting with the business models creation and validation</p>	
<p>Research and academia experts (e.g., AI experts etc.)</p>	<p>Contribution to the efficient development of the VPME solutions by providing valuable feedback on the solutions</p> <p>Offer opportunities for collaboration with other projects</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potential end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at a suitable venue in Burgas</p> <p>The training will be given by BURGAS and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>
<p>Companies, business and market experts</p>	<p>Assisting with bringing the AI4PublicPolicy solutions to market by incorporating them into their products and providing feedback on its performance in a real-world setting</p> <p>Assisting with the business model creation process</p> <p>Validation and evaluation of the business models at a later stage of the project</p>	<p>Training is required as they might be potent end-users of the integrated solutions</p> <p>The training will take place either remotely or physically at the BURGAS Municipality premises</p> <p>The training will be given by BURGAS and relevant technical project experts</p> <p>The training material is under development</p>

6.3 Ethical management activities completion

As part of the pilot preparation phase, all pilots are required to fulfil the ethical management tasks listed in the table below and described in more detail in the deliverables of WP9. As part of this deliverable, the BURGAS pilot provides a status report on the accomplishment of the tasks mentioned in the table below.

It is crucial to remember that in addition to carrying out the required ethical activities listed in the table below, continuing actions are also ongoing to ensure legal and ethical compliance and that the project conforms with applicable laws and regulations. In this direction, pilots work closely with the appropriate legal partners as needed to ensure they adhere to ethical principles.

Table 11. Ethical management activities completion of BURGAS Pilot

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Activity Deliverable of Reference Status (Done/Pending)	Deliverable of Reference	Status (Done/Pending)
The beneficiaries must confirm that they have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research	D9.1	Done
Before the beginning of data collection activities, an ethics committee opinion/authorisation on the activities, sources and procedures related to data collection and processing must be in place	D9.2	Done
A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted as a deliverable	D9.3	Done
A report describing the specific challenges and proposed solutions for deploying the piloted technology at a real scale with real data in real life while and in compliance with the project's ethical requirements must be submitted	D9.4	Pending (deliverable due M36)
Implement anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques	D9.5	Done
Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be kept on file	D9.6	Done
The pilot must list the personal data harvesting tools which will be used and confirm for each of them whether their policies comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements	D9.7	Done
A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing must be submitted	D9.8	Done
The pilot must evaluate the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project. This includes also an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 GDPR 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted	D9.9	Done
In D9.10, five issues have been discussed regarding the technology developed in the project: biases, accountability, literacy, quality of the data and policy validation. These issues have been discussed in the form of a questionnaire (see appendix III in D9.3)	D9.10	Done

7 Conclusions

Overall, the present report is a part of WP6, which is the WP responsible for implementing, validating, and evaluating the pilots' systems with the participation of the consortium's public authorities. This particular deliverable, which is the second in a series of two, focuses on the first objective of the WP6, which is to describe the preparations that pilots must do in order to deploy and operate the project's pilot systems at the five pilot locations.

The first thing we asked of the pilots was information on the infrastructure that would need to be deployed for the pilot operation. As previously said, some of the pilots moved forward with the deployment of equipment to gather raw data, while the remainder mainly relied on their existing data sources.

Pilots have also reported some preliminary plans for the HW/SW needed to access the VPME and EOOSC/EGI resources (such as dedicated working stations, etc.), which will be further finalised at a later time.

Additionally, pilots must determine whether local legacy systems that are already deployed and in operation at pilots' sites might need to be integrated with the AI4PublicPolicy pilot implementations. According to the feedback received, some of the pilots do not support any legacy systems that call for integrations, while others make use of systems of this nature that may require further integration at the next phases of the project.

The procedures put in place to make real-time datasets available to the implementation teams were also mentioned by the pilots. Pilots offer APIs that may be used into the AI4PublicPolicy Dataset Management Component in order to achieve this. The Policy and Dataset Catalogue allows users to access publicly accessible real-time data.

In addition, all pilots gave historical datasets for each of the datasets listed in D2.3, if appropriate, when discussing the historical data. As could be seen, the implementation teams were given historical datasets for the pilots in various formats (e.g., CSV, JSON etc.)

Apart from the deployment of the necessary equipment that differs from one pilot to another according to their needs, a common involvement and training plan has been developed for all pilots.

One of the main objectives of this plan is to actively involve citizens and NGOs in the policy creation, development, refinement and evaluation by giving voice to citizens and collecting their input to be possibly incorporated in the refinement of the policies. Aside from the engagement in the policy development and optimisation process, the citizens as well as other relevant stakeholders will play an important role in the development, validation and evaluation of the VPME technical solutions. To achieve this, at the next co-creation phases, they will be given the opportunity to test and interact with the tools and provide us with useful feedback that will guide future developments. Finally, pertinent beneficiaries will contribute to further explore business and market opportunities.

Last but not least, pilots gave us an update on the status of the ethical actions that must be completed in accordance with the WP9 deliverables to ensure compliance with all applicable ethical and legal obligations.

Taking all factors into account, it was easier to follow and track each pilot's progress related to the preparation activities and take corrective action as needed thanks to the standard rules and templates used to report pilots' preparation activities. The WP6 will continue to work closely with the pilots as the project advances to make sure that all pilots complete the necessary tasks in order to assure their preparedness for pilot operation.